

June 30, 2024

<https://ijoabs.com/>
[DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo)

Factors Influencing Consumers' Repurchase Intention Green Cosmetics in Vietnam: A Qualitative Study

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾ **Tran Thi Song Lam**-National Economics University

Email: ts4232qk@st.neu.edu.vn

⁽²⁾ **Le Ngoc Ha**-Minh Dam school

Email: haleevt2007@gmail.com

⁽³⁾ **Ha Tieu Linh**-Asian International School

Email: hatieulinh08072007@gmail.com

Received Date: 20-Mar-2024

Accepted Date: 27-April-2024

Published Date: 30-June-2024

Abstract:

The objective of this article is to evaluate factors impacting on consumers' repurchase intention green cosmetics of Vietnamese consumers based on qualitative research. The article conducted in-depth interviews with consumers who have purchased green cosmetics in the last 12 months. A total of 40 individuals are regular customers of green cosmetics and spa stores in Vietnam. In addition, the study conducted interviews with 5 experts in the Vietnam Natural Products Science Association. The data was compiled using Nvivo software and has summarized the factors affecting consumers' repurchase intention green cosmetics in Vietnam.

Keywords: Repurchase intention, green cosmetics, Vietnam

1. Introduction

According to estimates by Future Market Insights (FMI), the global green cosmetics market will reach a revenue of USD 79.6 billion by 2033, with sales growing at a modest compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.1% from 2023 to 2033. This market will reach \$48.4 billion by the end of 2023. The demand for green cosmetics will continue to increase as consumers become increasingly concerned about health and environmental awareness. Therefore, the increasing demand for green products along with the greater availability of green cosmetic products on genuine retail channels will drive the growth of the green cosmetics market in the coming years.

The green cosmetics market has a strong growth rate stemming from consumers' awareness of the harmful effects of synthetic ingredients. Customers are increasingly aware of the potential health risks associated with synthetic ingredients commonly found in cosmetics such as parabens, phthalates, and synthetic fragrances. With green cosmetics and beauty products becoming more prominent in the past few years, the concern about ingredients plays an active role in the sales of cosmetic products, which, in turn, will support the green cosmetics market well. The increased awareness of environmental protection has also had a positive impact on the growth of the green cosmetics market. This is because many consumers are looking for products that are produced sustainably and have a low impact on the environment.

June 30, 2024

Currently, many studies on consumer behavior towards green products have emerged but are mainly conducted in the US, Europe, Taiwan and Malaysia (Kim and Chung, 2011). Therefore, studies on the acquisition behavior of green cosmetics in Vietnam). Most studies use planned behavior theory as the basis theory to propose models. There are few studies that use consumer value theory for this topic. Consumer value theory can contribute to a common understanding of consumer choice behavior, and assist practitioners, policymakers, and academic researchers in determining which values are important to drive customer acquisition intent. Therefore, the author uses a combination of both theories to build a research model on the intention of Vietnamese consumers to buy green cosmetics. Therefore, the task of the studies is to find out the factors that affect consumers' intention to buy green cosmetics in order to propose solutions and strategies to stimulate customer consumption demand.

Sustainable consumption is becoming increasingly popular among consumers in the 21st century. Consumers are concerned about issues such as global warming, pollution, and animal abuse, leading them to consume eco-friendly products. Therefore, this increase in green consumerism is no longer a surprising change in today's society. Besides the trend of organic food, which is rapidly growing from a niche to a mainstream segment in the food sector, the demand for organic non-food products is also increasing. Today, consumers not only want to eat green, but also want to drive green, use green electricity, wear green clothes, use green detergents, and switch to green cosmetics/green cosmetics (Marangon et al., 2015). This increases ethical consumerism in all types of markets, suggesting a general ethical sensitivity in consumer purchasing decisions (Maggioni et al., 2013). Consumers turn to natural and organic products because they believe it is better for their own health and beneficial to the environment (Maragon et al., 2015)

An exciting area that is on the rise among green consumers is the green cosmetics market. Today, the green cosmetics market is the second-largest organic industry after organic food in some countries such as the United States, which is also leading the global green cosmetics market. Statistics show that the international growth rate for green cosmetics is higher than the rate of conventional cosmetics (Fonseca-Santos et al., 2015).

Although consumer demand for ecological products in general is now widely recognized by marketers and organizations, scientific research is limited and, if any, has mainly focused on the food sector (Testa et al., 2013). This lack of scientific research leads to very little evidence of consumers' underlying motivation to buy green cosmetics and what factors may be crucial for consumers to actually choose green cosmetics over conventional cosmetics.

Green cosmetics can offer a number of important benefits over conventional cosmetics, which makes research in this area just as important as research in the food sector. For example, research shows that some ingredients found in conventional cosmetics disrupt the hormonal system and increase the risk of cancer (Annis, 2011; Csorba & Boglea, 2011). Green cosmetic alternatives have been shown to have better safety measures than conventional cosmetics, meaning they are often manufactured with fewer synthetic or genetically modified ingredients (Annis, 2011; Kim & Chung, 2011).

In addition, green cosmetics are less harmful to the environment because they do not contain chemicals such as petroleum, aluminum, or microplastics. For example, the extraction of oil and aluminum is necessary in the Amazon rainforest. Moreover, ingredients such as microplastics contaminate our drinking water when we wash cosmetics from the body (Csorba & Boglea, 2011). Therefore, green cosmetics have similar characteristics and functions to conventional cosmetics, however less harmful to the environment and friendlier to our bodies (Fonseca-Santos et al., 2015).

In addition, previous research that really focused on consumer behavior in the field of green cosmetics has found conflicting results about what factors play a role in the decision-making process of purchasing green cosmetics: Tsakiridou et al. (2010) emphasized that consumers are becoming more and more conscious about environmentally friendly production methods schools, which influences their purchasing decisions for green

June 30, 2024

cosmetics. Kim and Chung (2011) advocate the influence of environmental consciousness. In contrast, Ong (2012) found that environmental protection is not the motivation when buying green cosmetics. This underscores the fact that additional research is needed to better understand consumers of green cosmetics. In general, different studies have found that different factors can influence the purchase intention and actual buying behavior of green cosmetics, such as the variables of the theory of planned behavior (attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral cognitive control), past behavior, health and environmental awareness and product-related knowledge (Kim & Chung, 2021).

2. Literature review

2.1. Green cosmetics

Along with the rapid development of the modern world, awareness of environmental impact as well as health trends towards green consumption models is increasing. This increases eco-friendly products, including cosmetic products made from natural ingredients, avoiding the use of chemical additives (Sreen et al., 2021; Zollo et al., 2021).

Although defined in many different ways with different names, in general, green cosmetics, natural cosmetics or eco-friendly cosmetics all contain the same elements. As affirmed in our research, eco-friendly cosmetics or green cosmetics are natural and organic cosmetic cosmetics. They contain natural and organic sources of ingredients, avoid synthetic chemicals, are packaged with eco-friendly or reusable materials, and focus on environmental protection. (Suphasomboon & Vassanadumrongdee, 2022)

Therefore, the author chooses to use the term "green cosmetics" uniformly throughout the entire project to facilitate research activities and define concepts.

In their research, green cosmetics consumers defined the term as cosmetics made from natural ingredients, which not only benefit personal use but also contribute to environmental protection. These consumers are motivated to buy green cosmetics not only for their own benefit but also for the purpose of protecting the surrounding environment. [Click or tap here to enter text.](#)

Green cosmetics are defined as products that are environmentally friendly and do not pollute or deplete natural resources. These cosmetics are also designed to be recyclable and promote sustainability. Our research has shown that green cosmetics often include natural products with plant-based ingredients. (Csorba & Boglea, 2011)

The European Union also launched the Organic and Natural Cosmetics Standard – COSMOS in 2008. This standard sets guidelines and criteria for certifying cosmetics as organic and natural, further promoting environmentally friendly practices in the industry to meet this trend. (D'Amico et al., 2008)

In summary, based on the definition of green products and studies on green cosmetics, it is possible to define green cosmetics as personal care products that are produced from natural ingredients, do not contain harmful chemicals, and are not tested on animals, in order to protect the environment and minimize impacts on nature. These products are often designed to be recyclable and promote sustainability, complying with international standards such as COSMOS to ensure naturalness and organicness.

2.2. Intention to Repurchase intention

Green acquisition intent is one of the elements of green behavior intent, which is an important factor that explains an individual's purchasing behavior towards a green product in the future. Green acquisition intention is the trend of consumers buying green products in the future. This behavioral intent is a strong indicator of future green purchasing behavior. Although this intent is not the same as the actual purchase, the green product acquisition intent can be used to determine the green buying behavior trend of customers. Green repurchase intent when compared to previous purchases is a relatively accurate method to predict customers' future green buying behavior (Chaudhary & Bisai, 2018; Woo & Kim, 2019)

June 30, 2024

In fact, research on customer acquisition intent is important for green businesses and green products. One of the first models to explain purchase intent and behavioral intent in general is based on rational action theory and is further developed into planned behavior theory. With recent developments in consumer behavior research, as in the study of shows that consumer behavioral intentions are explained based on the quality of products and services. Similarly, based on the cognitive-behavioral approach, the quality-based behavioral intent model is proposed, which assumes that the factors driving behavioral intention are product quality, perceived value, and satisfaction. Research suggests that while product quality is what consumers experience in terms of performance, the value of a product is their assessment of the benefits that the product offers, the perceived value and quality of the product will impact customer satisfaction. Recent studies on green products have also verified the link between quality, perceived value, satisfaction, and behavioral intent (Pahlevi & Suhartanto, 2020)

However, research on green cosmetics is still quite limited, including the outstanding research of . The study developed a conceptual model that links perceived values to green consumer attitudes, which in turn influences their purchase intent. In particular, by investigating the impact of attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral cognitive controls on acquisition intent, the 'attitude-intent' framework is examined and validated in the context of green care products, including green cosmetics. (Ghazali et al., 2017)

2.3. Factors affecting customers' Repurchase intention

Attitude towards behavior

To understand attitudes toward behavior, research first points to definitions of attitudes in general. According to , the definition of attitude is a relatively comprehensive and long-term assessment of an object, problem, person or action. Determining that attitudes are often viewed from the perspective of the evaluation function – determining whether something is good or bad, desirable or undesirable. Attitude is defined as the level of feeling of goodwill or no toward a particular product or brand when judging by personal thoughts, products, and purchase reviews from past experiences, such as customer service or brand awareness. Therefore, attitudes can impact specific human behaviors, especially towards specific brands or products. Mansour et al. (2016) have described attitude as the level of positive value or negative value for performance behavior. Similarly, it is also considered that attitude is the level of positive or negative emotions of a person towards the use of that particular product (Bashir & Madhavaiah, 2015)

(Schiffman & Kanuk, 2000) Explain that attitude has three components: perception, emotion, and action. Perception is knowledge and awareness gained from a combination of direct experience with the object and relevant information from different sources. Emotions are feelings or feelings about a particular product or brand. Action is the tendency by which an individual will behave in a certain way in relation to the object. Attitudes are the increasing or decreasing evaluations, tendencies and emotions of a person about an object or suggestion. From there, attitude towards has been defined as an individual's inner evaluation of an object such as a branded product. From there, it is argued that attitudes towards behavior have long been recognized as the most important factor in social psychology. Attitude towards behavior is also arguably the most important factor influencing acquisition intent. In addition, our study analyzed that attitude to behavior was the best predictor of acquisition intention expressed in 29 of the 30 studies. (Kotler & Armstrong, 2009)

According to Planned Behavior Theory - TPB, attitude is one of the four factors that predict behavior. Accordingly, the author has also defined attitude towards behavior as the degree to which a person has a positive or negative assessment of a particular behavior. The higher the positive level of a person's attitude towards a behavior, the less likely the person will be to commit it. The higher the negative level of the person's attitude, the more the person will intend not to perform the behavior. That is, the predictability of the execution based on the attitude about the behavior is assumed to be governed by the specific characteristics for the person who acts, the situation and the attitude that the person holds about the execution of that behavior. It is also noted that at any given time, attitudes towards a behavior are "determined by accessible beliefs about the

June 30, 2024

consequences of that behavior, known as behavioral beliefs." In describing the development of Planned Behavior Theory, it is proposed that the strength of attitudes is often determined by characteristics that are "closely similar to some of the sub-characteristics of attitudes that are thought to regulate the relationship between attitude and behavior" and include characteristics such as the importance of the attitude field, certainty in a holding position, direct or indirect experience with the object of attitude and investment in attitude. Attitude power plays a role in triggering attitudes; The stronger the attitude, the more automatic its activation will be. These more powerful attitudes are proposed to develop as a function of direct relation to the object of attitude as opposed to direct or indirect interaction with the object of attitude (Fishbein & Ajzen, 2011)

Previous studies have also confirmed that perceived value is always considered important when consumers buy a product, especially green products as in the scope of the subject's research e.g. the research of . To create a positive attitude towards a green product, the perceived value must be higher, and the product stated as a green product must have the highest value when consumers buy it. Indeed, green buying attitudes have a direct and positive effect on consumers' purchase intention as well as their intention to buy green products. In various studies, green buying attitudes are positively linked to green buying intentions. (Ghazali et al., 2017)

Subjective standards

According to Planned Behavior Theory, subjective norms or subjective norms are the second factor that predicts behavior. The subjective norm relates to the perceived social pressure of a person to perform a certain behavior. According to , subjective norms refer to the social pressure that an individual feels to perform or not to perform that behavior. Given that social pressure is a perceived pressure, this factor is called in theory as the subjective norm. Accordingly, it is important to understand which social group stands out at the time of making a decision to act. This is paramount because social pressure can vary depending on which social group is prominent at the time of decision-making. The premise of the subjective norm develops from the individual's belief that other significant people approve or disapprove of that behavior . Note that subjective norms operate as a global perception of social pressure. However, it has been shown that social pressure is rarely so direct or explicit, so many researchers have developed their own concepts of subjective norms (Ajzen, 2005)

Indeed, when individuals are in groups, there will be certain rules or norms or beliefs about proper consumer behavior. According to , consumers tend to have a positive intention to buy a product if they notice that the things that are important to them have a positive attitude and opinion about the product. According to , subjective standards have a certain degree of influence, affecting the intention to buy organic care products, which are safe for the environment. Acknowledging the results from previous studies, with the research object being consumers' intention to buy green cosmetics, subjective standards have a significant impact. Especially in today's era, when green cosmetics are being used and called for by more and more people to use them for the purpose of protecting the environment and reducing the impact on nature. This has been proven in a number of previous studies such as (Shimul et al., 2022)

Behavioral Cognition Control

Behavioral cognitive control, the third element in Planned Behavior Theory – TPB, is theorized to predict behavior and refers to an individual's perception of their ability to control behavior. has introduced the concept of self-empowerment, which refers to the belief that a person is capable of performing a certain behavior. According to Planned Behavior Theory, there is a relationship between behavioral cognitive control and intention to act . This admittedly existing relationship is based on the assumption that individuals who believe they do not have enough resources or opportunities to perform a behavior will find it difficult to act even if other factors suggest that action . also note that behavioral cognitive control can have a direct effect on behavior as well as have an indirect effect through intent. In short, behavioral cognitive control is a function of the ability to control the execution of an action, and that ability is based on the level of experience of that behavior, as well as the experience of a second or third party in controlling behavior and other related factors (Ajzen, 2005)

June 30, 2024

Within the scope of research with green products, behavioral cognitive control reflects the individual's perception of how easy or difficult it is to buy a green product. According to , it can be related to situational factors such as economic cost, availability of information about the product, availability of the product, or convenience and ease of use. It is highly unlikely that consumers will buy green products if they believe that the purchase is difficult or that the effort involved in purchasing green food products does not bring any benefits to the buyer or the environment. Many other studies have also found that controlling cognitive behavior affects the intention to buy, or the intention to buy green products. Similarly for green cosmetics, the legacy study looked at the impact of behavioral cognitive control factors on consumers' intention to buy green cosmetics (Witek & Kuźniar, 2023)

Consumer value

In today's dynamic market, consumer value has become one of the most important drivers of customers. Customer value is the fundamental foundation for all marketing activities. Refers to perception as the overall consumer evaluation of a product or service based on the perception of what is received (aka benefits) and what is offered (aka cost). It is often referred to as the ratio or trade-off between quality and price. In fact, the consumer experience of customers often involves the simultaneous interaction of many different value aspects (Holbrook, 2002)

For example, in influencing consumer choice, it proposes five aspects of value (social, emotional, functional, intellectual, and conditional value) to fully capture the cognitive and emotional nature of value. For the scope of the study, which is green products, the impact of these five values on customers' consumption choices of green products has also been studied and pointed out. It is also said that consumer reviews of products are not only based on quality and performance, but also take into account the enjoyment and joy derived from the product - emotional value, and social pressure on what the product conveys to others - social value. propose five consumer perceived values about health, safety, social, spiritual and environmental values that can influence customers' attitudes towards purchasing products. These value aspects are often independent of each other because they are complementary, complementary, and increasingly contributing to consumer choice (Ghazali et al., 2017)

Inheriting from previous studies, within the scope of the topic, the author proposes factors that affect the attitude towards customer acquisition behavior including: functional value, social value, emotional value, conditional value, knowledge value, safety value, environmental value. These factors are further stated in the sections below (Ghazali et al., 2017)

3. Research methods

The interviewees are consumers who have purchased green cosmetics in the last 12 months. A total of 40 individuals are regular customers of green cosmetics stores in Vietnam. In addition, the study conducted interviews with 5 experts in the Vietnam Natural Products Science Association.

Table 1. Statistics describing the interviewee

Criteria		Amount	Proportion
Age	< 19	7	17%
	[19; 25)	15	38%
	[25; 39)	10	25%
	> 40	8	20%
Gender	South	14	35%
	Female	26	65%
Total income	< 10 million/month	15	38%
	From 10 – 25 million/month	15	38%
	> 20 million/month	10	25%
SUM		40	100%

June 30, 2024

Source: Authors

The study was based on the average statistics of customers of green cosmetics stores (by age, gender, and total income) to select the interviewees. The age of the interviewees from 13 to 60 years old was divided into 3 groups: Adolescents (Under 19 years old) accounted for 17%, young people (From 19 to 24) accounted for 38%, young people (From 25 to 39) accounted for 25%, middle-aged (> 40) accounted for 20%. In terms of gender, female customers account for 60%, male customers account for 40%. This shows that women are still the subject of higher beauty care needs. However, the number of men accessing and using beauty products and services is increasing. In terms of total income, income groups are divided into 3 groups: (1) Less than 10 million/month (38%), (2) From 10 to 25 million/month (38%) and (3) More than 20 million/month (25%).

The interview process takes place from 15/12/2023 – 30/12/2023. The research has pre-standardised key interview questions based on the research model and the context of the current situation of Vietnam's cosmetics industry.

A semi-structured interview was conducted during the interview process. In Part One, the interviewees will be introduced to the topic and research objectives. After that, the personal information of the subjects is collected. Part 2, the interview content will revolve around the subject's perception of green cosmetics. Next, the study was carried out to take each person's assessment of the value of green cosmetics and their intention to buy green cosmetics in the future. In Part 3, the interviewees will exchange and express their opinions on the level of comprehensibility, language, and expression of the research scale. The adjusted scale table is used to serve the process of completing the questionnaire in the next period.

The study synthesized 56 pages of A4 data from 8 interviews (5 subjects each). The study conducted a comparison of manuscripts and recordings to synthesize and eliminate errors. These data will then be encoded and compared to find potential factors, as well as their suitability for the expected research model. The result of this period is a calibrated study scale and questionnaire.

4. Results of qualitative research

4.1. Results of consumer awareness and interest in green cosmetics

The results of the study show that most consumers have learned information about green cosmetics before buying and using. The level of interest and knowledge about green cosmetics of each object is different. The time to learn and know about green cosmetics ranges from a few months to more than ten years. Some people spend the first 1-2 years learning about green cosmetics before deciding to use them, because when green cosmetics began to be introduced, this product did not have much information and reliability. Others, mostly young people, have switched from conventional cosmetics to green cosmetics quickly because the product line has become popular and proven useful. Others know about green cosmetics thanks to trends and advertisements on social networks or used and recommended by friends and acquaintances.

The number of consumers during the interview process is selected based on the actual customer sex ratio at stores. In which, women account for the majority (65%). However, the results of the study show that the level of interest of men in green cosmetics is not too different from that of women. Many male consumers understand green cosmetics and beauty care knowledge very well.

"Skin care is no longer just for women. Young men invest in skin care is very popular and I am a typical example of it. I often learn about cosmetics and recently green cosmetics, I am very fond of shiny skin" – 24-year-old male customer.

"Young men are also afraid of aging now, but girls are still affected the most." – Female customer, 31 years old.

Objects have different definitions of green cosmetics. There are people who approach green cosmetics at the limit of natural composition. Others delve deeper into the green manufacturing process and the social responsibility of green cosmetics companies and brands.

"green cosmetics is a product derived from nature, trusted by benignness and safety." – Male customer,

25 years old.

"green cosmetics converges many precious plants, which are condensed into ingredients in beauty cosmetics. Some green cosmetics contain ginseng, red pine." - Female customer, 22 years old.

"green cosmetics has a certificate that the raw materials are natural ingredients and have a production process that does not harm the environment." -Male customer, 35 years old.

"In green cosmetics, not only are the ingredients from nature, but the entire process from planning to production, packaging and distribution must also be environmentally friendly." - Female customer, 27 years old.

"green cosmetics is different from chemical cosmetics in that chemical substances are gradually replaced with natural ingredients such as: Herbal essential oils, milk, fruits, turmeric, cucumbers, aloe vera, seaweed, honey, etc." - Male customer, 27 years old.

The results show that each subject has a different level of interest in green cosmetics, from basic information to specialized knowledge. Some subjects said that they went to some factories to directly observe the green cosmetics production process. Others share that they have been making simple cosmetics at home such as fruit masks, aloe vera leaf moisturizers, oatmeal cleansers, rose toners, etc.

The study classifies the interest level of the subjects based on self-assessment and the level of understanding of the audience about green cosmetics.

Table 2. The level of interest in green cosmetics of the interviewees

Level of interest	Amount	Proportion
Little interest	6	15%
Normal	11	27.5%
Very interested	23	57.5%
Sum	40	100%

Source: Authors

Table 2 shows that the percentage of consumers who are very interested in green cosmetics accounts for the majority (57.5%). These are subjects with extensive knowledge of green cosmetics beyond the content published on social networks, and have the habit of searching for information regularly. Those with a normal level of interest accounted for 27.5% and little interest was 15%.

4.2. Results of consumer perception of the value of green cosmetics

The study was conducted to take consumers' evaluations of the value of green cosmetics. In this content, the interviewees will give knowledge and evaluations about green cosmetics – different from the causes – motivations that motivate them to use green cosmetics in the next section. The results show that most consumers agree that green cosmetics bring many benefits to consumers. Some subjects have considered the relationship between the value of green cosmetics and the environment and social community. Specifically, the study conducted interviews with open-ended questions, so that the subjects were free to express their views. Then, based on the theory of consumer value and items from the research of Lin and Huang (2011) to collect a full opinion on the values: functional value, social value, emotional value, conditional value and cognitive value.

The interviewees all said that green cosmetics is a type of product created to bring safety to consumers. Some individuals argue that green cosmetics is not only composed of natural ingredients, minimizes harmful chemicals, and the production, packaging, and distribution processes are also carried out according to green standards.

"Most of the major cosmetic brands in Vietnam today have green cosmetics lines. From skin care, hair care to makeup, with investment in the whole process and strict testing experts. No chemicals; No synthetic ingredients, etc., those are the characteristics that make green cosmetics a trend today." - Male customer, 25

June 30, 2024

years old.

"green cosmetics has highly medicinal ingredients, but it is safe because of the increasingly advanced production process." - Female customer, 45 years old.

Some people think that green cosmetics is more effective than regular cosmetics. Since green cosmetics are more benign than chemical cosmetics, they are compatible with most skin types. Using green cosmetics is towards sustainable beauty.

"green cosmetics is loved not only for its safety, but also for its high efficiency." - Female customer, 41 years old.

"green cosmetics has a big advantage; That is the ability to be compatible with all skin types. Unlike ordinary cosmetics, green cosmetics does not cause skin irritation, and is used by all subjects." - - Female customer, 17 years old.

"The advantage of the green cosmetics is that it can be compatible with a lot of skins and has a high safety index. The purity that comes from the natural source of nutrients of green cosmetics is the attraction to consumers." - Male customer, 27 years old.

green cosmetics is also recognized for its environmental benefits. With the environment, green cosmetics's materials and production processes are said to minimize environmental harm. The production process does not produce as many harmful substances as conventional cosmetics. Some green cosmetics companies use compostable or paper packaging. Others believe that promoting the green image also makes green cosmetics companies and brands more interested in social and environmental responsibility. In addition, some interviewees said that green cosmetics is humane because it is not tested on animals.

"Because cosmetics must be tested for safety before being put on the market. Usually this process will be tested on animals. Those who love animals will not have this happen. This is why green cosmetics is considered a humane product because it is not tested on animals, but through experts and modern technological equipment." - - Female customer, 47 years old.

"Wastewater from chemical cosmetics will adversely affect the environment. On the contrary, the use of green cosmetics will help improve and protect the environment." - Female customer, 27 years old.

"green cosmetics doesn't just limit chemicals, but its ingredients come from farms. Therefore, the more green cosmetics is produced, the more plant density increases, resulting in less negative environmental impacts." - Male customer, 32 years old.

"The advantage of green cosmetics is its harmony with the environment, including the production and packaging process. In addition to limiting packaging with plastic materials and recycled materials, many cosmetic brands have developed innovative product forms, reducing product packaging area such as toothpaste." - Female customer, 45 years old.

green cosmetics was born to replace conventional products because of its environmental friendliness. *"Petroleum is often the source of many common cosmetic ingredients. The use of oil needs to be exploited on a large scale, causing the soil environment to be affected, and wildlife to be deprived of their habitat. In contrast, natural products, including green cosmetics, all come from plants. The diverse use of green materials requires animal habitats to maintain biodiversity, thereby sustaining plant species."* – Expert on green products. This is also one of the contents of the conditional value mentioned by Lin and Huang (2012).

When prompted about the social value of green cosmetics, some interviewees said that green cosmetics builds its own value standards in the field of beauty care. From those who believe and use green cosmetics, they will show their faith and spread it on social media or word of mouth and spread the value of sustainable beauty, *"turning others into wiser consumers"*.

"The green cosmetics trend has spread a good message about healthy beauty. green cosmetics consumers will express their consumer beliefs on social media. As a result, the trend towards consumer value has been shown by them with positive actions." - Female customer, 27 years old.

"green cosmetics brings a green lifestyle, a clean lifestyle. Nowadays, people are starting to pay more attention to health and lifestyle, especially when vegetarianism and clean living are being applied by many

June 30, 2024

people in their daily lives. And using this green cosmetics also extends to the aspect of not conducting animal testing." - Female customer, 25 years old.

"By consuming green cosmetics, consumers not only take care of themselves, but also contribute to protecting the environment and supporting local communities. This helps to promote a sense of sustainability and create a more responsible consumer community." – Client nm, 34.

"Some green cosmetics companies support local communities by purchasing ingredients from farmers or local communities, creating opportunities for work and economic development in rural areas," said a 31-year-old female customer.

In terms of social value, the subjects said that using green cosmetics makes them feel more confident and better perceived by others because it brings an image of green and clean living. In terms of cognitive value, interviewees said this is a confusing, unclear term because *"it's not easy to see right away."* Therefore, the study replaced the cognitive value with the environmental value and the safety value.

In short, the results of consumer interviews all said that green cosmetics has brought benefits to the community and society. The subjects are quite fully aware of the value of green cosmetics. These include functional value, social value, emotional value, condition value, safety value and environmental value.

4.3. Interview results on consumers' criteria for choosing to buy green cosmetics

Each customer will have a different concern and criteria to choose to continue using green cosmetics. Some people are interested in the price, but some people only ask about the use and quality of the product. The first thing that makes people continue to use green cosmetics stems from its values. In particular, the issue of safe and effective products is something that consumers are particularly interested in.

"Taking care of yourself is one of the ways to love yourself. When it comes to taking care of yourself, it's always important to choose the right and safe products." - Female customer, 19 years old.

"Ordinary cosmetics are not suitable for your skin, or chemicals can lead to premature skin aging. Therefore, benign cosmetics and safe products are my No. 1 choice to get a sustainable look." - Male customer, 26 years old.

"green cosmetics, of course, has natural extracts. Such as fruits, minerals, plants. In terms of safety for me, this is the first choice." - Female customer, 45 years old.

"In the past two years, I have always prioritized looking for cosmetics extracted from nature. From melaleuca cleanser, rose water, moisturizing palm oil to centella essence. These products are both easy to buy, close to nature and benign. So I completely switched to using natural cosmetics for peace of mind." - Male customer, 26 years old.

"Thanks to strict research and testing regulations, combined with selected natural ingredients and high-tech active ingredients, green cosmetics can treat, regulate, and restore problems such as acne, melasma, freckles, aging, etc., while maintaining the health and beauty of the skin that ordinary cosmetics cannot do." - Female customer, 29 years old.

"The skin has been damaged with a number of manifestations such as thin skin, acne easily, many wrinkles, uneven skin color, dark spots, and dehydration,... It will be very difficult to recover if you only use conventional skin care cosmetics. It is necessary to use green cosmetics safely to promote efficiency." - Female customer, 41 years old.

"green cosmetics Safe was born as a result of research that has been committed and certified for effectiveness and safety by reputable doctors, pharmacists, and dermatologists. Each ingredient included in the product must be used in the right concentration and not have a negative impact on human health. Therefore, I trust green cosmetics. Once I have used green cosmetics, I don't want to go back to regular cosmetics." - Male customer, 34 years old.

Some people believe that the fact that cosmetic brands do a good job in green image is a big plus point for them to become loyal consumers. These subjects will be aware of the impact of green cosmetics use on the environment.

June 30, 2024

"In the high-end cosmetics segment, Dior is also a shining light towards the environment. In recent years, Dior has gradually eliminated nylon covers from products as well as minimized the amount of paper and cardboard used in packaging." - Female customer, 46 years old.

"Not stopping there, many companies also focus on using environmentally friendly packaging with recyclable materials with the aim of reducing negative impacts on the environment." - Female customer, 35 years old.

"Many brands also launch products that incorporate ESG (Environmental, Social and Governance Standards Reporting) management policies, emphasizing the values of "safety", "ethics" and "sustainability"." – Expert in green products.

Animal lovers said they used green cosmetics for humanitarian reasons, not for animal testing. *"Typically, cosmetics will be tested on animals to ensure they are safe and effective to use. This procedure is too cruel because it endangers laboratory animals. With green cosmetics, the technology devices will be verified by experts, not using animals – this is a plus point for me to use green cosmetics, besides the environmental aspect."* - Male customer, 28 years old.

"With green cosmetics, most companies are tested by experts for safety and effectiveness with advanced technology without harming animals." - Female customer, 32 years old.

Besides, some people said that green cosmetics usually costs more than regular cosmetics. They will consider continuing to use green cosmetics depending on the promotional campaigns of the airlines.

According to experts in the organization..., the reason for the trend of using green cosmetics is thanks to the spread and support of society. In particular, the most affected people are young people. *"The next reason for the trend of using green cosmetics is the Gen Z generation (those born after 1990). This generation includes young people who are between the ages of 20 and 30 years old. This is the generation with a large number of social network users and is one of the generations that are quite active in environmental protection activities. They are also consumers of social media influencers. After the pandemic, instead of just pursuing the value of "external beauty", they have turned into wise consumers, buying products with "social value."* – Green product expert.

"Teenagers are consumers who don't have much experience and they are easily influenced. Therefore, young people will be more easily influenced by social norms and beauty instincts." - Female customer, 41 years old.

In addition to consumer values, the study conducted a survey of subjects about their behavioral perceptions, attitudes, and subjective standards towards green cosmetics acquisition. In particular, most attitudes towards the acquisition of green cosmetics are positive, and the choice to acquire green cosmetics will largely depend on whether they are interested and want to use it again. For those who are already financially independent, they can decide for themselves whether to continue using green cosmetics. Many people said that it would depend on controlling their monthly spending or the availability of the cosmetics they wanted. Others said they use green cosmetics because they are persuaded by people around them such as friends, colleagues, and relatives.

The results show that consumer values are one of the main reasons why consumers trust and continue to use green cosmetics. In particular, young people are mainly influenced by trends and social networks, people with high living standards tend to be interested in SCR, the environment, and most of them are interested in safety and health.

4.4. Results of consumers' intention to buy green cosmetics

The study conducted a survey on the intention to use green cosmetics of interviewees within 12 months. The results are shown in table 3

Table 3. Statistics describing the interviewee

Criteria		Amount	Percentage of people who intend to buy green cosmetics
Age	< 19	7	71%
	[19; 25)	15	80%
	[25; 39)	10	50%
	> 40	8	75%
Gender	South	14	72%
	Female	26	65 %
Total income	< 10 million/month	15	73%
	From 10 – 25 million/month	15	67%
	> 20 million/month	10	70%
Level of interest	Little interest	6	50%
	Normal	11	73%
	Very interested	23	87%
SUM		40	100%

Source: General Research

The interview results show that young people have a great interest in green cosmetics. Especially in the digital age, when information is spread rapidly with the development of the marketing industry, young people are affected by trends and social impacts. The trend of green and clean living is not only a concern for adults, but they are being actively received by young people. In other words, age is not a barrier for consumers to access green cosmetics again.

In terms of gender, although women are more strongly affected by beauty issues, men are now also gradually paying more attention to external beauty. Especially for individuals involved in jobs that require external relations, taking care of appearance does not discriminate between genders.

Besides, according to the research results, the level of income has no obvious effect on consumers' intention to buy green cosmetics. Some people with lower incomes are still willing to spend more money on cosmetics than some people with better incomes. Specifically, a newbie with an income of 8 million/month is willing to pay 3 million for beauty products (i.e. the cost for green cosmetics can account for 37.5% of their salary). While another interviewee with an income of 12 million is only willing to pay less than 1 million VND for cosmetics.

In contrast, the larger the interest in green cosmetics, the higher the rate of intention to buy green cosmetics. Based on the above results, the study chose the interest level variable as the regulator for the research model.

5. Conclusion

The latest data shows that the growth rate of the middle-class population in Vietnam is the fastest in Southeast Asia thanks to factors such as economic growth, rising living standards, improvements in education and health, and other social policies. It is expected that the proportion of the population belonging to the middle class will double today by 2026. As personal income increases, the demand for beauty care will also increase. Thereby, reflecting the trend of spending more on improving the beauty and personal health of consumers when they are better financially able. This will make an important contribution to the development of the Vietnamese market in the field of cosmetics.

June 30, 2024

Figure 1. Revenue of Vietnam’s cosmetics retail market in the period 2018 – 2027 (billion VND)

Source: Beautycareexpo (2023).

In the latest document from Statista in Vietnam, 2022 recorded a revenue of 2.2 billion USD for the cosmetics market, and it is expected that this figure will exceed the threshold of 2.6 billion USD by 2027. The annual growth rate of Vietnam's cosmetics market in the period of 2024 – 2027 is also estimated at a positive figure of 3.32%. The demand for cosmetics in Vietnam is increasing, leading to the emergence of more and more cosmetic distribution stores, including direct and online distribution. This creates a fierce competition to achieve the goal of driving profits in the Vietnamese cosmetics market. Stores are also getting more and more creative in combining potential cosmetics to gain a competitive advantage in improving the new customer experience.

Figure 2. Frequency of use of cosmetics by age

Source: CleverAds (2022)

June 30, 2024

According to the report, the average monthly cost for beauty care of age groups in Vietnam is as follows:

- For the group from 25 to 32 years old, the average cost is about 700,000 VND, which is the highest level among the three groups.
- For the group from 33-39 years old, the average cost is about 610,000 VND, which is the second highest level among the three groups.
- For the group aged 40 years and over, the average cost is about 590,000 VND, the lowest of the three groups.

Thus, the age group from 25-32 is the most potential customer in building a cosmetics consumption market, with a better willingness to pay than the rest of the age groups.

Vietnam is increasingly attracting the attention of famous cosmetic brands around the world. South Korea ranks first in exporting cosmetics to Vietnam, followed by European powers. Vietnam also imported about \$950 million worth of beauty products in 2019 from other exporters including Singapore and China. Popular imported items for women include cleansers, lipsticks, and moisturizers. Besides, there are also a number of products for men such as grooming and shaving.

The main reason for the dominance of multinational corporations in the market is mainly due to the preference for imported goods from Vietnamese consumers. Customers in Vietnam appreciate international brands because of the high product quality as well as the variety, which is able to meet individual needs. The expansion of the retail network through chain stores such as Watsons and Guardian, along with the emergence of new competitors such as Pharmacy and Matsumoto, has facilitated access to imported cosmetic products for consumers mainly from the middle class and above in Vietnam. In addition, thanks to realizing the development potential of the Vietnamese market, large foreign cosmetic corporations have opened representative offices or distributed products through agents and distributors such as Unilever accounting for 12% of the market share or L'Oreal.

Not only stopping at the dominance of imported goods, Vietnamese cosmetic brands are also gradually strengthening their position in the past 2 years thanks to the development of a large number of domestic cosmetic brands. A prominent example is M.O.I Cosmetics - a Vietnamese cosmetics brand founded by celebrities Ho Ngoc Ha and Lam Thanh Kim. This brand has risen to become the only Vietnamese business present in the Top 10 makeup cosmetics market share in 2022. Notably, M.O.I's market share has increased sharply to 3.2% (2022) while the daily number is only from 0.9% in 2018, almost on par with one of the leading names in the cosmetics industry, Revlon. Starting from the number of 30,000 lipsticks, M.O.I has now developed a series of 20 beauty care product lines, with a supply of more than 4 million products. The company has also expanded its distribution network to include 90 stores nationwide and cooperates with thousands of distribution partners. Currently, the main product and product line that plays an important role in the success of the M.O.I brand is still lipstick thanks to the important position of this cosmetic in the beauty needs of the market. In addition, Baby Skin Cushion is also a product that has contributed an important part to the transformation in M.O.I's business sales.

Brands such as Thai Duong, Cocoon, ... have also recorded significant growth in the cosmetics industry in Vietnam recently. This development is mainly rooted in the expansion of the domestic cosmetics industry and the focus on research and development of high-quality products. In addition, the use of organic, nature-derived cosmetics is becoming increasingly popular. This is evidenced by the success of the Cocoon product. Consumers are paying more and more attention to the use of natural cosmetics that are healthy for their skin and are also very interested in cosmetics that do not harm the environment.

The results of the study show that the eye and lip product line currently occupies a leading position in the market, bringing in more than \$100 million in revenue per year since 2018. In contrast, the natural cosmetics sector is still operating at a lower level, but there is still great growth potential in the near future. The proof is that more and more people are paying their attention to natural, organic, and herbal ingredients, believing that they are more beneficial to health and environmentally friendly than conventional cosmetics.

June 30, 2024

Pharmaceutical and cosmetic products derived from nature of Vietnamese brands are attracting more and more trust from customers. Some brands such as Cocoon, Laco, Thai Duong... This is evidenced by the significant increase in profits of domestic brands in recent years. Moving on to 2024, this trend is not only continuing, but also increasing. However, this brings a new wave to the cosmetics market. With less competition for display space, now is the ideal time for businesses to launch new products. Several trends are receiving increased attention, including a focus on sustainable production, trust (by celebrities), product personalization, inclusivity, and the use of clean ingredients. For example, cosmetic brands such as Cocoon, a business in Nature Story Cosmetics Co., Ltd., were born in 2013. Cocoon is known as an herbal brand, completely made from natural resources and made in Vietnam. According to data from Vietdata (2023), in just 2 years, Cocoon's revenue has increased from about VND 13 billion in 2020 to VND 184 billion in 2022 and achieved a record profit after tax of 46.6 also in 2022.

Vietnam has the advantage of diverse raw materials and reasonable production costs

As an agricultural country, Vietnam is proud to own a variety of plants and herbs that can be applied in the production and development of green cosmetic products. According to information from the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, Vietnam has more than 10,000 species of plants with about 1,000 of them being particularly suitable for the production of green cosmetics such as oranges, aloe vera, grapefruit, cucumbers, tomatoes, lemons, etc. Other medicinal plants such as chamomile, green tea, rose, turmeric, etc., or grape seed oil plant extract products, such as coconut oil, etc., are also very suitable for inclusion in the production of green cosmetics.

The green and sustainable living movement is spreading in Vietnam

Consumers in Vietnam are increasingly interested in using environmentally friendly products, including natural cosmetics.

Encouraging policies from the Government

The Vietnamese government has implemented policies to encourage the development of the cosmetics industry in general and the export cosmetics industry in particular. This has played an important role in promoting the development of the cosmetics market in Vietnam.

E-commerce is growing

E-commerce is playing an increasingly important role in the cosmetics and beauty industry in Vietnam. More and more consumers are shopping for beauty products online, which makes it easier for them to access more brands and products.

The cosmetics market in Vietnam is experiencing instability

The fierce competition between domestic and foreign brands is creating a fierce competitive environment in the cosmetics market. This means that the market is constantly moving, from trends to prices and product quality. This instability poses major challenges for businesses in developing and executing their business strategies. Companies must be able to adapt quickly to market changes to maintain their competitive position.

Consumers in Vietnam are interested in the price of products

Consumers in Vietnam often consider the price before deciding to buy. Therefore, businesses need to pay attention to controlling production costs to be able to compete effectively in the market. Moreover, consumers in Vietnam also prioritize products with affordable prices and reliable quality. Therefore, businesses need to focus on improving product quality to meet the desires of green cosmetics consumers.

REFERENCES

- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Ajzen, I. (2005). Attitudes, Personality and Behavior. In *Mapping social psychology*.

June 30, 2024

Akbar, W., Hassan, S., Khurshid, S., Niaz, M., & Rizwan, M. (2014). Antecedents Affecting Customer's Purchase Intentions towards Green Products. *Journal of Sociological Research*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.5296/jsr.v5i1.6566>

Alix, T., & Vallespir, B. (2010). A Framework for Product-Service Design for Manufacturing Firms (pp. 644–651). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-16358-6_80

Al-Swidi, A., Mohammed Rafiul Huque, S., Haroon Hafeez, M., & Noor Mohd Shariff, M. (2014). The role of subjective norms in theory of planned behavior in the context of organic food consumption. *British food journal*, 116(10), 1561-1580.

Amberg, N., & Fogarassy, C. (2019). Green Consumer Behavior in the Cosmetics Market. *Resources*, 8(3), 137. <https://doi.org/10.3390/resources8030137>

Amos, C., Pentina, I., Hawkins, T. G., & Davis, N. (2014). "Natural" labeling and consumers' sentimental pastoral notion. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 23(4/5), 268–281. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBM-03-2014-0516>

Baek, E., & Oh, G.-E. (Grace). (2021). Diverse values of fashion rental service and contamination concern of consumers. *Journal of Business Research*, 123, 165–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.061>

Bashir, I., & Madhavaiah, C. (2015). Consumer attitude and behavioural intention towards Internet banking adoption in India. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, 7(1), 67–102.

Bauer, H. H., Heinrich, D., & Schäfer, D. B. (2013). The effects of organic labels on global, local, and private brands. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(8), 1035–1043. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2011.12.028>

Biswas, A., & Roy, M. (2015). Leveraging factors for sustained green consumption behavior based on consumption value perceptions: testing the structural model. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 95, 332–340.

Bloomberg. (2016). J&J Must Pay \$72 Million Over Talc Tied to Woman's Cancer. Bloomberg.

Boksberger, P. E., & Melsen, L. (2011). Perceived value: a critical examination of definitions, concepts and measures for the service industry. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 25(3), 229–240.

Boxall, A. B. A., Rudd, M. A., Brooks, B. W., Caldwell, D. J., Choi, K., Hickmann, S., Innes, E., Ostapyk, K., Staveley, J. P., Verslycke, T., Ankley, G. T., Beazley, K. F., Belanger, S. E., Berninger, J. P., Carriquiriborde, P., Coors, A., DeLeo, P. C., Dyer, S. D., Ericson, J. F., ... Van Der Kraak, G. (2012). Pharmaceuticals and Personal Care Products in the Environment: What Are the Big Questions? *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 120(9), 1221–1229.

Boxall, A., Rudd, M.A., Brooks, B.W., Caldwell, D.J., Choi, K., Hickmann, S., Innes, E., et al., 2012. Pharmaceuticals and personal care products in the environment: what are the big questions? *Environ. Health Perspect.* 120 (9), 1221–1229.

Chakraborty, D., Siddiqui, M., & Siddiqui, A. (2022). Can initial trust boost intention to purchase Ayurveda products? A theory of consumption value (TCV) perspective. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 46(6), 2521–2541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijcs.12805>

Chandra, T., Hafni, L., Chandra, S., Purwati, A. A., & Chandra, J. (2019). The influence of service quality, university image on student satisfaction and student loyalty. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 26(5), 1533–1549. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-07-2018-0212>

Chang, Y., & Geng, L. (2022). Planned or unplanned purchases? The effects of perceived values on omnichannel continuance intention. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 50(12), 1535–1551. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJRDM-01-2021-0012>

June 30, 2024

- Chaudhary, R., & Bisai, S. (2018). Factors influencing green purchase behavior of millennials in India. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 29(5), 798–812.
- Chen, H.-S., & Hsieh, T. (2011). A study of antecedents of customer repurchase behaviors in chain store supermarkets.
- De Toni, D., Eberle, L., Larentis, F., & Milan, G. S. (2018). Antecedents of Perceived Value and Repurchase Intention of Organic Food. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 24(4), 456–475. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2017.1314231>
- Dörr, J., Wagner, T., Benlian, A., & Hess, T. (2013). Music as a service as an alternative to music piracy? An empirical investigation of the intention to use music streaming services. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 5, 383–396.
- Garg, P., & Joshi, R. (2018). Purchase intention of "Halal" brands in India: the mediating effect of attitude. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 9(3), 683–694. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-11-2017-0125>
- Ghazali, E., Soon, P. C., Mutum, D. S., & Nguyen, B. (2017). Health and cosmetics: Investigating consumers' values for buying organic personal care products. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 39, 154–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2017.08.002>
- Jamrozy, U., & Lawonk, K. (2017). The multiple dimensions of consumption values in ecotourism. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 11(1), 18–34. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCTHR-09-2015-0114>
- Joibi, N. S. B., & Annuar, S. N. S. (2021). The Impact of Consumption Values Towards Intention to Visit Green Hotel (pp. 159–172). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65147-3_11
- Kim, H. Y., & Chung, J. E. (2011). Consumer purchase intention for organic personal care products. *Journal of consumer Marketing*, 28(1), 40–47.
- Kim, K.-H., & Park, D.-B. (2017). Relationships Among Perceived Value, Satisfaction, and Loyalty: Community-Based Ecotourism in Korea. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 34(2), 171–191. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2016.1156609>
- Kumar, S., Dhir, A., Talwar, S., Chakraborty, D., & Kaur, P. (2021). What drives brand love for natural products? The moderating role of household size. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 58, 102329. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102329>
- Laroche, M., Bergeron, J., & Barbaro-Forleo, G. (2001). Targeting consumers who are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 18(6), 503–520.
- Lee, Y.-K., Lee, C.-K., Lee, W., & Ahmad, M. S. (2021). Do hedonic and utilitarian values increase pro-environmental behavior and support for festivals? *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 26(8), 921–934. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10941665.2021.1927122>
- Li, G., Yang, L., Zhang, B., Li, X., & Chen, F. (2021). How do environmental values impact green product purchase intention? The moderating role of green trust. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28, 46020–46034.
- Limbu, Y. B., Pham, L., & Nguyen, T. T. T. (2022). Predictors of Green Cosmetics Purchase Intentions among Young Female Consumers in Vietnam. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12599. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912599>
- McMillan, E. E., Wright, T., & Beazley, K. (2004). Impact of a University-Level Environmental Studies Class on Students' Values. *The Journal of Environmental Education*, 35(3), 19–27. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JOEE.35.3.19-27>

June 30, 2024

- Megantara, I. M. T., & Suryani, A. (2016). Determine the intention to buy back flight tickets online on the traveloka website. com. *E-Journal of Management of Udayana University*, 5(9), 5783–5810.
- Meier, B. P., Dillard, A. J., & Lappas, C. M. (2019). Naturally better? A review of the natural-is-better bias. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 13(8). <https://doi.org/10.1111/spc3.12494>
- Midmore, P., Naspetti, S., Sherwood, A.-M., Vairo, D., Wier, M., & Zanoli, R. (2005). Consumer attitudes to quality and safety of organic and low input foods: a review. Report of EU-Funded Project "Improving Quality and Safety and Reduction of Cost in the European Organic and 'Low Input' Food Supply Chains." Univ. Wales, Aberystwyth, UK.
- Minh Ly Duc, Le Vu Duc Anh, Le Thanh Duy, Huynh Hai Dang, & Nguyen Hoang Tuan. (2023). Factors Influencing Gen-Z's Intention to Buy Green Cosmetics in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam. *International Journal of Engineering Technology and Management Sciences*, 7(5), 248–259. <https://doi.org/10.46647/ijetms.2023.v07i05.029>
- Muhamed, A. A., Ab Rahman, M. N., Mohd Hamzah, F., Che Mohd Zain, C. R., & Zailani, S. (2019). The impact of consumption value on consumer behaviour. *British Food Journal*, 121(11), 2951–2966. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-10-2018-0692>
- Oestreicher-Singer, G., & Zalmanson, L. (2013). Content or community? A digital business strategy for content providers in the social age. *MIS Quarterly*, 591–616.
- Olsen, J., Thach, L., & Hemphill, L. (2012). The impact of environmental protection and hedonistic values on organic wine purchases in the US. *International Journal of Wine Business Research*, 24(1), 47–67. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17511061211213783>
- Olsen, J., Thach, L., Hemphill, L., 2012. The impact of environmental protection and hedonistic values on organic wine purchases in the US. *Int. J. Wine Bus. Res.* 24 (1), 47–67.
- Onel, N. (2017). Pro-environmental Purchasing Behavior of Consumers. *Social Marketing Quarterly*, 23(2), 103–121. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524500416672440>
- Purba, D. A. K. (2015). The Role of Brand Community in the Formation of Consumer Repurchase Interest. *Journal of Application Management*, 13(1), 17–24.
- Qasim, H., Yan, L., Guo, R., Saeed, A., & Ashraf, B. (2019). The Defining Role of Environmental Self-Identity among Consumption Values and Behavioral Intention to Consume Organic Food. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(7), 1106. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16071106>
- Ramkissoon, H., Nunkoo, R., & Gursoy, D. (2009). How consumption values affect destination image formation. In *Perspectives on cross-cultural, ethnographic, brand image, storytelling, unconscious needs, and hospitality guest research* (pp. 143–168). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Raska, D., & Shaw, D. (2012). Is the Greening of Firms Helping Consumers to Go Green? *Social Marketing Quarterly*, 18(1), 40–54. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1524500411435482>
- Regner, T. (2015). Why consumers pay voluntarily: Evidence from online music. *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Economics*, 57, 205–214.
- Shapoval, V., Murphy, K. S., & Severt, D. (2018). Does service quality really matter at Green restaurants for Millennial consumers? The moderating effects of gender between loyalty and satisfaction. *Journal of Foodservice Business Research*, 21(6), 591–609. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15378020.2018.1483698>
- Simão, S. A. V., Rohden, S. F., & Pinto, D. C. (2022). Natural claims and sustainability: The role of perceived efficacy and sensorial expectations. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 34, 505–517. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.09.026>

June 30, 2024

- Sreen, N., Dhir, A., Talwar, S., Tan, T. M., & Alharbi, F. (2021). Behavioral reasoning perspectives to brand love toward natural products: Moderating role of environmental concern and household size. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 61, 102549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102549>
- Statista. (2020). Global Market Value for Natural and Organic Cosmetics and Personal Care in 2018–2027. Statista.
- Sudrajad, G., & Mudiantono, M. (2014). Analysis of the Influence of Brand Image, Price, and Product Quality on Repurchase Interest (study on Buck store in Semarang) (Doctoral dissertation, Faculty of Economics and Business).
- Suhartanto, D., Brien, A., Primiana, I., Wibisono, N., & Triyuni, N. N. (2020). Tourist loyalty in creative tourism: the role of experience quality, value, satisfaction, and motivation. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 23(7), 867–879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2019.1568400>
- Suhartanto, D., Kartikasari, A., Arsawan, I. W. E., Suhaeni, T., & Anggraeni, T. (2022). Driving youngsters to be green: The case of plant-based food consumption in Indonesia. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 380, 135061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135061>
- Suphasomboon, T., & Vassanadumrongdee, S. (2022). Toward sustainable consumption of green cosmetics and personal care products: The role of perceived value and ethical concern. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 33, 230–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.07.004>
- Van Loo, E. J., Diem, M. N. H., Pieniak, Z., & Verbeke, W. (2013). Consumer attitudes, knowledge, and consumption of organic yogurt. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 96(4), 2118–2129. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2012-6262>
- Witek, L., & Kuźniar, W. (2023). Green Purchase Behaviour Gap: The Effect of Past Behaviour on Green Food Product Purchase Intentions among Individual Consumers. *Foods*, 13(1), 136. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods13010136>
- Woo, E., & Kim, Y. G. (2019). Consumer attitudes and buying behavior for green food products. *British Food Journal*, 121(2), 320–332. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-01-2018-0027>
- Xu, A., Wei, C., Zheng, M., Sun, L., & Tang, D. (2022). Influence of Perceived Value on Repurchase Intention of Green Agricultural Products: From the Perspective of Multi-Group Analysis. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 15451. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215451>
- Zollo, L., Carranza, R., Faraoni, M., Díaz, E., & Martín-Consuegra, D. (2021). What influences consumers' intention to purchase organic personal care products? The role of social reassurance. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 60, 102432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102432>